

Call for papers

Advanced Nanoscience and Technology: An International Journal (ANTJ) is a peer-reviewed, open access journal, addresses the impacts and challenges of Nanoscience and Technology. The journal documents practical and theoretical results which make a fundamental contribution for the development of Nanoscience and Technology.

Topics of Interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Micro / Nano Fabrication and Metrology
- Micro / Nano Heat Transfer and Energy Information Technology,
- Micro / Nano Sensors , Actuators and Systems Nanobionics
- Micro / Nanofluidics and Bio Chips
- Modeling and Simulation
- Molecular Sensors, Actuators and Systems
- Nano and Molecular systems
- Nano Robotics, Assembly and Automation
- Nano-bio-informatics, Nanomedicine
- Nanobiology / Nanobiomechanics / Nanobiotechnologies
- Nanocatalysis
- Nanoelectronics
- Nano-Graphene
- Nanomaterials, Nanodevices: Fabrication, Characterization and Application
- Nanomedical Applications: Drug Delivery, and Tissue Engineering
- Nanophotonics
- Nanotechnology and Agriculture / Coating / Education / Energy
- Nanotechnology and Environment / Polymer
- Nanotechnology, Products and Markets
- Societal aspects of Nanotechnology: Ethics, Risk Assessment, Standardization

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : December 14, 2019**
- Acceptance Notification : January 14, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due : January 22, 2020
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : antj_journal@yahoo.com or antj_journal@airccse.com

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